

two 6-m rows 50 cm apart in a split-plot design with 2 replications. Fifty to 60 seeds/linear meter were used. Grain yield was used to rate tolerance and susceptibility. Tolerance for aluminum toxicity (Al_t) was calculated as:

$$Al_t = \frac{\text{Yield in limed plot} - \text{yield in unlimed plot}}{\text{Difference of Al-saturation without and with lime at flowering}}$$

The yield of the high-aluminum plot and its Al_t , are plotted in the figure. Average yield at the high-aluminum level and Al_t were calculated. The diagram is divided into quadrants representing the four groups of cultivars by lines of average yield on high-aluminum plots and average Al_t .

Cultivars that yielded well under high aluminum level and responded well to added lime were: Fernandes, IAC46, Santa Amélia, IAC21, IAC 1246, IAC1131, KN361-1-8-6, IR2070-199-3-6-6, IAC101, IRAT104, Paulista, IR4727-217-3, IR4227-240-3-2, IAC165, CN770532, CN770527, CN770820, CN770167, CN770610, CN771204, Dular, Pinulot 330, Catgo, and Chatão.

Cultivars that produced well under high aluminum level but did not respond to added lime were IRAT13, IAC120, 6 Meses, IAC12, IPSL2060, Grão de Ouro, Rendimentos, Bicudo, Salumpikit, Mogi, Sequeiro do Paraná, IAC5544, EEPG569, IR4829-2-1, IAC5100, Montanha Liso, Pratão Goiano, Seleção Amarelão, CN770867,

CN770858, CN770643, CN770614, CN770893, CN770546, CN770602, CN770531, DJ29, AG10-37, IAC5032, and Canta Galo.

Cultivars that produced less under higher aluminum level but responded to added lime were: IAC47, Amarelão, IAC25, Taiwan, Três Potes, Arcos Branco, Baixada, BKN6652-249-1-1, Dourado Precoce, IET6058, C22, Precoce Amarelo, Cana Roxa, Lageado, KN144, IR5793-54-2, C12, Serra Azul, B1293b-PN-24-2-1, H14, IR3483-180-2, IR4707-207-1, IR4227-9-1-6, Azucena, CTG 15 16, CN770530, CN770191, CN770447, Batatais, Catalão 101, Prata, Taquari, Rondon, Campineiro, and Milagres. ✎

Effect of ferrous sulfate application on rice yield and iron uptake

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A pot culture experiment was conducted on calcareous (pH 8.7, organic carbon 0.56%, $CaCO_3$ 4.7% and 11.4 ppm DTPA-Fe) and noncalcareous (pH 8.5, organic carbon 0.17%, $CaCO_3$ 0.25%,

and 8.7 ppm DTPA-Fe) soils (Aeric Fluvaquent) during summer 1979 to study the effect of $Fe SO_4 7H_2O$ soil applications (0, 15, 30, and 60 ppm) on the yield and Fe uptake of rice in submerged conditions.

Grain yield increased 35% at 15 ppm and 70% at 30 ppm added Fe for calcareous soil and 100% and 200% for noncalcareous soil (see table). Straw yield increased significantly up to 15 ppm added Fe in noncalcareous soil

and up to 30 ppm in calcareous soil. The significant decrease in yield at higher rates may be attributed to the antagonistic effect of Fe on the availability of other nutrients. Fe application of up to 30 ppm increased Fe uptake in straw and grain in both soils. Uptake in grain continued to increase up to 60 ppm Fe in calcareous soil. Total Fe uptake was greater in calcareous soil than in noncalcareous soil, which was the reverse of yield trends. ✎

Effect of different rates of iron on dry matter yield (grain and straw) and iron uptake by PR-106, Punjab, India.

Rate of iron (ppm)	Yield (g/3-kg pot)				Iron uptake (mg/3-kg pot)			
	Calcareous soil		Noncalcareous soil		Calcareous soil		Noncalcareous soil	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
0	1.7	5.4	1.7	10.1	0.27	2.85	0.22	1.79
15	2.3	7.9	3.4	14.0	0.44	3.52	0.52	3.32
30	2.9	11.3	5.1	11.7	0.74	7.06	1.04	4.43
60	2.5	9.0	2.8	10.4	0.98	5.92	0.53	2.32
C.D. (0.05)	0.4	1.0	0.5	1.7	0.17	0.49	0.19	0.34

Effect of phosphorus fertilization and soil moisture regimes on phosphorus content of rice crop

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Different phosphorus (P) application rates were tested for their effect on rice

Table 1. Characteristics of 4 acid soils in Assam, India.

Soil	PH	Texture	Organic carbon (%)	Total P (ppm)	Available P (kg/ha)
Dergaon	5.0	Sandy loam	0.93	875	4.2
Golaghat	4.3	Clayey	1.57	1000	3.8
Tengakhat	4.5	Sandy loam	1.53	1563	3.9
Titabar	4.9	Clayey	1.33	1250	2.3

plant P concentrations at different development stages and moisture regimes. Soils from 4 areas in Assam,

India, were studied in the greenhouse at 3 levels of applied P: 0, 26.4 kg, and 52.8 kg/ha (Table 1). Moisture regimes

Table 2. Effect of P fertilization and moisture regimes^a on P concentration and dry matter yield in some acid soils of Assam, India, 1978.^b

Location of soil	P concentration (%)						Dry matter yield (g/pot)					
	Continuous submergence			Continuous moist			Continuous submergence			Continuous moist		
	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha
Titabar	0.136	0.182	0.215	0.093	0.090	0.114	13.13	28.80	34.13	6.97	20.83	17.87
Dergaon	0.171	0.307	0.326	0.093	0.131	0.156	21.80	23.60	36.10	9.87	14.57	13.50
Golaghat	0.185	0.264	0.310	0.110	0.117	0.139	23.20	34.27	30.80	13.10	16.00	16.87
Tengakhat	0.250	0.327	0.361	0.088	0.133	0.151	41.53	48.57	47.77	13.70	20.37	19.27
Mean of all soils	0.186	0.270	0.303	0.096	0.118	0.140	24.92	33.81	37.20	10.91	17.94	16.87
	C.D.(5%) Moisture regimes: 0.0089 Phosphorus levels: 0.0109						C.D.(5%) Moisture regimes: 3.17 Phosphorus levels: 3.88					

^aContinuous submergence: 5-7 cm standing water; continuous moist: moisture tension, 0 bar. ^bAt max tillering stage. Av of 3 replications.

Table 3. Effect of P fertilization and moisture regimes^a on P concentration of grain and yield of rice grain in some acid soils of Assam, India, 1978.^b

Location of soil	P concentration (%) in grain						Grain yield (g/pot)					
	Continuous submergence			Continuous moist			Continuous submergence			Continuous moist		
	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha
Titabar	0.276	0.278	0.324	0.235	0.213	0.211	13.30	21.83	22.90	4.43	6.47	9.57
Dergaon	0.248	0.312	0.366	0.190	0.168	0.264	15.37	18.47	18.50	6.77	9.70	11.13
Golaghat	0.215	0.312	0.367	0.191	0.142	0.215	16.63	21.97	24.30	7.33	11.10	10.17
Tengakhat	0.292	0.349	0.373	0.157	0.188	0.247	22.60	24.33	27.77	7.63	11.30	10.63
Mean of all soils	0.258	0.315	0.358	0.193	0.178	0.234	16.97	21.65	23.37	6.54	9.64	10.37
	C.D.(5%) Moisture regimes: 0.021 Phosphorus levels: 0.026						C.D.(5%) Moisture regimes: 1.30 Phosphorus levels: 1.60					

^aContinuous submergence: 5-7 cm standing water; continuous moist: moisture tension, 0 bar. ^bAt grain ripening. Av of 3 replications.

were continuous moist and continuous submergence.

Phosphorus application significantly increased P concentration in dry matter at maximum tillering stage at both moisture regimes (Table 2), but P concentration was higher in continuous submergence. Dry matter yield increases corresponded with increased P concentration under continuous submergence in all four soils. Results were similar in

continuous moist condition, but P concentration and dry matter yield were lower at each level of P application.

P applied to submerged soils caused significant increases in P concentration of grain at ripening stage and increased yield (Table 3). However, in continuous moist condition, there was no such consistency. In 3 of 4 soils, 26.4 kg P/ha decreased P concentration and increased yield, which suggests that yield increase

was achieved by dilution of the plant P concentration. At 52.8 kg P/ha, there was a significant increase in the P concentration in all the soils except that from Titabar. Grain yield increased in Titabar and Dergaon and decreased slightly in Golaghat and Tengakhat.

Results suggest that phosphorus application and continuous submergence improve rice crop performance. *h*

Use of azolla and commercial nitrogen fertilizer in Jorhat, India

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Complementary use of azolla and commercial nitrogen fertilizer for rice culture is receiving interest because of the global energy crisis. A 2-year experiment at Jorhat showed that incorporating 5 t fresh azolla/ha just before planting increased yields of Pusa 33 (1979) and Pusa 2-21 (1980) 44% over the control (no nitrogen, no azolla) (see table).

Mean grain yield of rice as affected by incorporation of azolla with and without nitrogen fertilizer, Jorhat, India.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Azolla incorporation		Yield (t/ha)	
	t/ha	Time	Pusa 33 (1979)	Pusa 2-21 (1980)
0	0	—	1.8	1.7
0	1 ^a	After planting	2.5	2.3
0	5	Before planting	2.6	2.5
0	10	Before planting	3.0	2.9
30	5	Before planting	3.4	3.3
30	10	Before planting	3.7	3.5
30	0	—	2.8	2.4
60	0	—	2.9	3.0
LSD (5%) in t/ha			0.6	0.4

^aFresh azolla was inoculated after planting, allowed to grow and then incorporated after 20 days.